

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF EGFR RECEPTORS IN DIFFERENT MOLECULAR BIOLOGICAL SUBTYPES OF BREAST CANCER

Kahharov A.J. ¹

Narzieva D.F. ²

¹ Associate Professor of Tashkent State Dental Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

² Basic doctorate of Bukhara State Medical Institute, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

alisher1510@mail.ru, noza_2206@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960311>

Introduction. It is now recognised that the molecular subtypes of breast cancer have a significant impact on diagnosis, prognosis and choice of therapeutic strategies. Each subtype has unique biological features that may determine sensitivity to different treatment modalities, including chemotherapy, hormone therapy and immunotherapy [1,2] Immunotherapy is the main new treatment for breast cancer (BC). However, not all breast cancer patients benefit from immunotherapy. Prognostic biomarkers of immunotherapy, such as tumor mutational burden and tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes, are promising for stratifying patients with breast cancer and optimizing the therapeutic effect. Different targets of the immune response pathway have also been investigated to expand the potential of immunotherapy[3,4]. Therefore, the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of breast cancer depending on immunologic characteristics and the role of immunotherapy are still a subject of research [2].

Purpose of the study: To study the features of EGFR receptor expression in different molecular and biological subtypes of breast cancer

Materials and methods. The study included 102 breast cancer patients who were under dispensary supervision in conditions of Tashkent city branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology. We performed an IHC study of EGFR marker. The strength of association between categorical indices was assessed using Cramer's V, the values of which were interpreted according to the recommendations of Rea & Parker (2014). Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results. EGFR status was analysed according to molecular biological subtype. According to the table presented, when analysing EGFR status according to molecular biological subtype, significant differences ($p < 0.001$) were found (method used: Pearson's Chi-square). The association between molecular biological subtype and EGFR status was relatively strong (Cramer's $V = 0.67$).

Conclusion. Our study demonstrates significant differences in EGFR receptor expression depending on the molecular biological subtypes of breast cancer. The

findings suggest a statistically significant strong association between EGFR status and molecular biological subtype (Cramer's $V = 0.67$, $p < 0.001$), which may be an important factor in the development of personalised therapeutic approaches for female breast cancer patients.

References:

1. Gok Yavuz B. et al. Cancer associated fibroblasts sculpt tumour microenvironment by recruiting monocytes and inducing immunosuppressive PD-1+ TAMs //Scientific reports. – 2019. – T. 9. – №. 1. – C. 3172.
2. Li J. J., Tsang J. Y., Tse G. M. Tumor microenvironment in breast cancer—updates on therapeutic implications and pathologic assessment //Cancers. – 2021. – T. 13. – №. 16. – C. 4233.
3. Turner K. M. et al. Heterogeneity within molecular subtypes of breast cancer //American Journal of Physiology-Cell Physiology. – 2021. – T. 321. – №. 2. – C. C343-C354.
4. Vranic S. et al. PD-L1 status in breast cancer: Current view and perspectives //Seminars in cancer biology. – Academic Press, 2021. – T. 72. – C. 146-154.

